

OPPORTUNITIES FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF BUKHARA OASIS ETHNOTOURISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098553>

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada Buxoro vohasida etnoturizmni rivojlantirish istiqbollari, imkoniyatlari, shart -sharoitlari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek hududda joylashgan Shirin qishlog'ining voha turizmi rivojiga qo'shgan hissasi haqida fikr yuritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *turizm, etnoturizm, Vobkent, Shirin qishlog'i, uy mehmonxonasi, hunarmandchilik ustaxonalari.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются перспективы, возможности и условия развития этнотуризма в Бухарском оазисе. Также обсуждается вклад села Ширин, расположенного в районе, в развитие оазисного туризма.*

Ключевые слова: *туризм, этнотуризм, Вобкент, село Ширин, домашняя гостиница, ремесленные мастерские.*

Abstract. *This article analyzes the prospects, possibilities, and conditions of the development of ethnotourism in the Bukhara oasis. Also, the contribution of the village of Shirin, located in the region, to the development of oasis tourism is discussed.*

Keywords: *tourism, ethnotourism, Vobkent, Shirin village, home hotel, craft workshops.*

Tourism is developing on a large scale all over the world, as it develops, it is enriched with new destinations and tourist spots. At the same time, tourism as a useful industry is taking place in our lives as a certain mechanism for revitalizing and modernizing not only the economy, but also the entire society. In the context of globalization and internationalization of culture, the problems of preservation, development and restoration of the historical and cultural heritage of various nations are becoming increasingly important.

Human qualities such as inquisitive nature and desire for knowledge are his inseparable characteristics. The humanitarian significance of tourism lies in the use of its opportunities for personal development, increasing creative potential, expanding knowledge and enriching the spiritual sphere.

Tourism allows you to successfully combine recreation with knowledge of the lifestyle, history and culture of another nation. Seeing the world with one's own eyes, learning, hearing, feeling the uniqueness of the culture of other peoples are important components of the restoration function of tourism, and they are distinguished by their great humanitarian potential.

Acquaintance with the way of life and customs of another country or region enriches a person's view of the spiritual world. Culture is the basis of the process of development, preservation and strengthening of national independence, sovereignty and identity. According to the position of UNESCO, tourism is one of the main factors of cultural and humanitarian development and contributes to maintaining peace and bringing people closer by establishing "dialogue between cultures".

On October 17, 2003, the International Convention on the Protection of Material and Cultural Heritage was adopted. The two-day World Tourism and Culture Conference signed by representatives of UNESCO, World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) on December 12, 2017 in cooperation with UNESCO, UNWTO and the Sultanate of Oman was an important event in the

development of tourism. Various delegations, the private sector, the local community and the Muscat Declaration on Tourism and Culture NGO were established to promote sustainable development.

Within the framework of the declaration, about 30 ministers and deputy ministers of tourism and culture from different countries, as well as 800 participants from 70 countries, confirmed their commitment to strengthening the synergy of tourism and culture and promoting the contribution of cultural tourism until 2030.

Uzbekistan, along with other countries, is actively trying to develop cultural tourism. The Declaration aims to formulate a cultural tourism policy that not only empowers local communities, but also uses innovative new tourism models that ensure sustainable development, host-guest cooperation, and cultural exchange.

The Declaration promotes the integration of sustainable cultural tourism and cultural heritage protection into national, regional and international security systems. The Declaration is based on the 1972 UNESCO Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage and the 2005 Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions.

Human values - peace, mutual understanding and mutual respect not only between different states, but also between peoples living on the borders of the same state - these are important social priorities and a fertile ground that nurtures and develops tourism.

In recent decades, tourism has actively developed, deepened diversification, and become one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy. The vector of tourism development has changed in recent years. Tourism has become more accessible to millions of people around the world, moving from a long-awaited summer vacation to an affordable year-round vacation. At the same time, tourism has ceased to be just a festive entertainment and has manifested itself as a new type of knowledge about the culture and traditions of the people, and has acquired the form of spiritual and physical development.

The transition of tourism from one category to another is the beginning of the process of branching tourism into several areas and regions, which contributed to the development of ethnographic tourism. Self-awareness and knowledge of the surrounding world, personal development and achievement of goals cannot be imagined without knowledge in the field of culture. The concept of "traditional folk culture" is applied to various forms of folk art that have been formed over the centuries of ethnic development. Today, when many elements of traditional culture are disappearing, the need for its scientific study and popularization is obvious.

In order to study the folk culture, ethnic tourism is based on cultural values, including many historical, architectural, literary, archeological monuments, as well as small historical towns included in the tourist program, participation in holidays, festivals, folk festivals, etc., and rural settlements. based on endless curiosity.

Ethnographic tourism is one of the rapidly developing branches of tourism business in modern Uzbekistan. It includes visits to places that are important for understanding the past, national culture and its present, and that allow to demonstrate the cultural identity of a certain group of people. It is not just about participating in national holidays and festivals. The purpose of ethnographic tourism is to study the way of life of a particular nation, people and their specific characteristics. Ethnotourism allows you to see and learn about the life of the people "from the inside" - to feel, live and study its history, traditions, rituals, language and legends.

At the same time, the main principle of such tourism is "do no harm", it is important to preserve natural, social and cultural diversity, promote it both inside and outside the country. Ethnographic tourism is often organized in places of traditional residence and economic activity of local peoples and is a means of developing traditional economy.

For example, in the framework of the decision of May 19, 2018 "On measures to rapidly develop the tourism potential of Bukhara region and Bukhara city in 2018-2019", the craft potential, rich traditions and customs of our people were demonstrated.

Within the framework of the festival, "Bukhara national crafts schools, including the Gijduvan pottery school in the Poyi Kalon complex, the Toqi Zargaron, the Bukhara brass carving school at the Nadir Devon Begi madrasa, the Nadir Devon Begi madrasa, the Sovga goldsmith center, "Master classes of the Bukhara School of Goldsmithing of the Goldsmith's Factory will be organized. In addition, the process of silk carpet weaving was demonstrated at the silk carpet center, and at the "Abdulazizkhan" blacksmithing school of Bukhara, and at the "Kokaldosh" madrasas, the master classes of the Shafirikon embroidery school were demonstrated. With little effort, the city has become a great tourism brand. According to its age, it is one of the oldest cities of Central Asia located on the Silk Road.

Vobkent district is considered one of the regions with rich tourist potential of Bukhara region, it is located 20 kilometers from Bukhara city, along the M-37 international highway. In 2022, the working group headed by the deputy governor of the region, Botirjon Shahriyrov, will visit the regions of the region with high tourism potential, and will increase the non-traditional tourism services provided to foreign and local tourists and improve their quality. inspected the works.

It should be noted that the village of Shirin has a history of about 1500 years, and its name comes from the names of 92 Uzbek clans. It is noteworthy that the unique history, ancient structures and national traditions of the villagers have been preserved to this day.

In the establishment of an ethnic tourism cluster, such values as the process of making pickles, dried fruits, national sweets, sugarcane crops, and handicrafts are passed down from generation to generation in the village.

There are a number of opportunities for tourists from abroad to demonstrate the rural lifestyle. The officials were charged with the task of creating a model ethnotourism center, additional tourist services, and developing a 1-3 day tourist package for this tourism village, and according to the prepared plan, necessary recommendations were given.

Currently, in order to turn the village of Shirin into a tourist destination, roads and tourist infrastructure facilities along the road have been repaired, gas and electricity networks have been renovated, and beautification works have been carried out. At the same time, based on the requirements of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5781 of August 13, 2019, it is planned to establish 20 family guest houses in the region.

To date, about 10 local initiators have received applications to establish a family hotel.

The process of grinding corn and wheat flour in an ancient mill in the Shirin village, baking bread and somsa in the oven, planting 20 different types of rice crops and creating a garden with fruit trees, preparing 5 herbs, a fishing pond and pets It is planned to establish a livestock corner. At the same time, the process of biologically growing fruits and vegetables, drying and packing them, wool spinning and making woolen products, local food using the natural products of the farms for tourists, as well as the cluster of making pickles, fruit peels and dairy products, it is

planned to show their master classes, cultural performances of national folklore groups, to organize a museum of ancient objects reflecting village life and a corner of national handicrafts.

In addition, the establishment of shops selling souvenirs, along with accompanying-interpreter services throughout the ethnotourism village, parking services for vehicles, and fishing in the lakes around the ethnotourism village, ancient construction of the ethnotourism center, which includes the construction of sandal houses, the direct participation of guests in the preparation of national products such as shordanak and nisholda, has been started.

In addition, in the center of the village there is a supermarket, pharmacy, beauty salon, information center, sewing shop, tour operator office, postal service, air and railway ticket office, souvenir shop, electrical workshop, hairdresser, confectionery and national sweets. The construction of the modern "Shirin tourism complex" household service house, which includes a preparation shop, a family guest house, a shoe repair shop, a clothing store, a national tea house, a bicycle rental center and a bakery, is being carried out in compliance with the quarantine rules.

It should be noted that in accordance with the appeal of the President of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, the "Tourism Neighborhood" and "Tourism Village" are being developed in the districts (cities) of Bukhara region with high tourism potential. The purpose of the establishment is to increase the number of objects on various new routes that can be developed in this area.

To sum up, in the following years, the continuous work carried out by such initiators and enthusiastic and selfless representatives of the field, who aim to make a worthy contribution to the further enrichment of the tourism potential of the region, to the development of the industry, will bear fruit. will become a new destination for tourists visiting Bukhara region in the future.

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